

Clinician, patient, and carer views on neuromodulation for epilepsy: is there rationale for a randomised controlled trial of DBS vs. VNS?

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Abstract:

Purpose

This study aimed to gather UK clinician, patient, and carer perspectives on vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) and deep brain stimulation (DBS) to inform the design of clinical trials to compare these treatments for patients with drug resistant epilepsy (DRE).

Methods

Two surveys were conducted: one targeting UK clinicians in neurology, neurophysiology, and neurosurgery, and another distributed to patients and carers.

Results

The clinician survey received 32 responses. They agreed that VNS (100%) and DBS (94%) have a role and in treating DRE. While 84% agreed there was enough evidence to support the routine use of VNS, that figure was only 23% for DBS. The mode of the minimum age to consider treatment was 5 years for VNS and 18 years for DBS. Clinicians agreed on the proposed trial's scientific validity (median Likert score 4/5) and interest to know which of the two treatments is more efficacious (5/5). 72% clinicians would support such a trial by referring eligible patients.

The patient/carer survey received 38 responses. A third were likely to consider VNS (32%) and DBS (34%). Key concerns for both treatments included procedure anxiety, side effects, and battery changes. 53% said they would be willing to enter the proposed DoVE trial, although 84% would prefer to choose which treatment they received.

Respondents in both surveys considered reduced seizure frequency, seizure freedom, quality of life, and reducing SUDEP risk as key outcomes measures.

Conclusion

Clinician, patient, and carer insights highlight the need for robust evidence on DBS and VNS efficacy. These findings will shape future studies aiming to establish the roles of these neuromodulation treatments in managing DRE.

Introduction:

Despite many new antiseizure medications (ASM) in the last 30 years, the proportion of patients with drug-resistant epilepsy (DRE) remains steady at approximately 30% (1). The insignificant decrease in population of DRE patients highlights the unmet need for non-pharmacological interventions (1).

Vagus nerve stimulation (VNS) is an established therapeutic intervention, typically achieving optimal efficacy around the sixth month of treatment, with 45–65% of patients experiencing a 50–100% reduction in seizure frequency (2). Some studies suggest that the effectiveness of VNS increases with treatment duration (3–7).

Landmark clinical trials, such as the E03 and E05 trials, have demonstrated the efficacy and safety of VNS in DRE patients (8). Conversely, DBS is an emerging option approved by the FDA in 2018 for adults with epilepsy and shows promise in specific patient populations (9). The SANTE trial (Stimulation of the Anterior Nucleus of the Thalamus in Epilepsy) and the ESTEL (Electrical Stimulation of Thalamus for Epilepsy of Lennox–Gastaut phenotype) trial are pivotal studies that established the efficacy of deep brain stimulation (DBS) in reducing seizure frequency in patients with DRE (10,11).

The National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence (NICE) recommendation (2020) for DBS for refractory epilepsy in adults varies depending on the site of stimulation. Clinicians should perform anterior thalamic DBS only with special arrangements for clinical governance, patient consent, and thorough auditing or research, owing to limited evidence. For other targets, they should undertake such procedures exclusively within the context of research, given the lack of sufficient evidence. (12). Currently, direct comparative data between VNS and DBS is limited, with much of the data drawn from single-center, retrospective studies. One recent study (13) reported that ANT-DBS (DBS targeting the anterior nucleus of the thalamus or ANT) provided a greater reduction in seizure frequency than VNS over a 12-month follow-up period, while another (14) highlighted variations in seizure reduction across different neurostimulation techniques and suggested that cortical stimulation strategies may offer some advantages over subcortical options, including ANT-DBS and VNS.

Given the lack of robust comparative data, clinician and patient perspectives are crucial in assessing the readiness for wider adoption of DBS and identifying patient-centred priorities in treatment design. Clinicians' perspectives help gauge medical community acceptance of DBS, reflecting their confidence and willingness to support this innovative intervention. Similarly, insights from patients and caregivers illuminate the real-world impact of these treatments, capturing essential feedback on quality of life, perceived benefits, and logistical challenges. This feedback is invaluable for designing patient-centred clinical trials, ensuring studies address relevant clinical endpoints and quality-of-life outcomes (15).

The proposed DoVE Trial (DBS or VNS for Epilepsy) is a randomised controlled trial comparing the efficacy of VNS and DBS for DRE. This study aims to gather perspectives from clinicians, patients with epilepsy, and their caregivers to inform such a trial's design and development.

As part of this study, surveys were conducted to gather perspectives on neuromodulation for DRE from key stakeholder groups. These included UK medical consultants treating epilepsy, as well as individuals with epilepsy and their carers. The aim was to capture both professional

and patients' personal views on the use of neuromodulation as a treatment option and assess interest in participating in the proposed DoVE trial.

By gathering insights through surveys this study aims to contribute to the optimization of epilepsy treatment strategies, serving as a guide to the development of the DoVE trial which will establish the roles for DBS and VNS in the management of drug-resistant epilepsy.

Methods:

Two online surveys were conducted. Both consisted of a mix of question types, including single best answer, multiple answer, Likert scales and free text answers. PDF copies of the two surveys are included in the Supplementary material.

Clinician Survey:

A piloted online survey was designed and distributed via online channels and mailing lists of relevant specialty associations including the Society of British Neurological Surgeons, the Association of British Neurologists, the British Society of Clinical Neurophysiology, the British Society for Stereotactic and Functional Neurosurgery, the British Branch of the International League Against Epilepsy and the British Paediatric Neurology Association. It was stipulated that only consultants in (adult or paediatric) neurology, neurophysiology or neurosurgery were eligible to complete the survey. Survey responses were collected between December 2023 and February 2024.

The survey had 4 sections:

Section 1: Demographic Information

Section 2: Views on role of VNS for drug-resistant epilepsy

Section 3: Views on role of DBS for drug-resistant

Section 4: View on a potential UK multi-center randomised trial of DBS and VNS

Patient/carer Survey:

A piloted online survey, with an embedded video (link included in the Supplementary material) explaining the treatments and a proposed trial to compare the two, was distributed to the patient/carer e-mail lists of relevant associations within the UK including the Epilepsy Research Institute's SHAPE network, Young Epilepsy and Epilepsy Action. The survey was distributed between January and March 2024.

The survey had 4 sections:

Section 1: A short video will explain current and future treatments for epilepsy.

Section 2: Questions about the person with epilepsy.

Section 3: Views about current and future stimulation treatments for epilepsy.

Section 4: View about the proposed DoVE trial.

Data Analysis:

Descriptive reporting of summary statistics and data visualisation of survey responses were conducted on R Studio and Microsoft Excel. Bar charts summarize categorical data, Likert plots illustrate scaled responses from 1 to 5, and the raincloud plot depicts the distribution of clinician-reported minimum ages for neuromodulation therapies. The raincloud plot combines a half-violin (distribution), a box plot (medians and interquartile ranges), and a dot plot (individual responses).

Results:

The clinicians survey received 32 responses, and the patients/carers survey received 38 responses.

Clinician Survey:

Demographics (section 1):

In the clinicians' survey there were 13 (40.6%) responses from specialists in neurosurgery, 13 (40.6%) from neurology and 6 (18.8%) from neurophysiology. Most of the clinicians (43.8%) had been a consultant for 10-12 years, 37.5% clinicians had been a consultant for less than 10 years and 18.8% had been a consultant for over 20 years. Responses were gathered from across the UK, with the highest representation being in Greater London (25%), followed by Southeast (21.9%), and Yorkshire and Humber (12.5%). The complete demographic characteristics of the survey respondents are detailed in Table 1 (see Supplementary Material).

Section 2-4:

All 32 (100%) of the clinicians agreed that VNS has a role in the treatment of drug-resistant epilepsy and 30 (93.8%) agreed that DBS has a role in the treatment of drug-resistant epilepsy. When considering what types of epilepsy may benefit from VNS, more than 84.4% respondents thought it would be beneficial for focal and generalized epilepsy. Clinicians seem to think DBS is less beneficial overall, with 70% agreeing that it is beneficial for focal epilepsy (Figure 1A).

Majority of respondents (68.8%) said that the minimum age to consider VNS as a treatment is 5 years or less with the median age being 5 years, while the responses for minimum age to consider DBS are quite varied with an interquartile range of 13 years, and the modal age being 18 years (Figure 1B).

Figure 1. Clinician views on neuromodulation as a treatment for drug-resistant epilepsy. A, paired bar chart shows the count of responses on the potential benefit of VNS and DBS for various epilepsy types, allowing a comparison between the two treatments. B, raincloud plot displays the distribution of clinician-reported minimum ages for considering VNS and DBS.

According to the survey, 84.4% of clinicians said that there is currently enough evidence to support the routine use of VNS while only 22.6% thought there was enough evidence to support the routine use of DBS as a treatment for drug-resistant epilepsy. With regards to VNS, respondents commented that the absence of randomised controlled trial data is a significant gap, and while there are ongoing studies, evidence remains stronger for focal seizures compared to generalized seizures. For DBS, respondents said the evidence is still developing and there is a clear need for data from a randomised clinical trial.

The clinicians were asked about their views on a potential study, a UK multi-centre randomised trial of DBS and VNS. They were asked to report their opinions about the design of the trial on a Likert scale of 1-5, illustrated as a Likert scale plot (Figure 2A). Clinicians agreed that the potential trial has scientific validity (median = agree; 87.5% agreed/strongly agreed), is of clinical interest (median = strongly agree; 93.7% agreed/strongly agreed), and they would refer patients to it (median = agree; 71.9% agreed/strongly agreed), while the median response for whether it was ethical to randomise was neutral (31.3% neutral and 50.1% agreed/strongly agreed).

While 50% of the respondents thought the primary endpoint should be the percentage reduction in seizures, other factors like seizure freedom, quality of life, and health-economic outcomes were also considered important (Figure 2B).

Figure 2. Clinician (n=32) views on potential randomised trial. A, Likert plot summarizes clinician opinions on aspects of the potential trial design and shows the overall sentiment regarding the proposed trial. B, bar chart shows the clinician responses regarding the preferred primary endpoint for the trial and highlight which endpoints are considered most important by clinicians when evaluating the trial's success.

Patient/carer:

Demographics (section 2):

In the patients’/carers’ survey, 71.1% responses were from persons with epilepsy while the rest were from a carer for someone with epilepsy. There were fairly equal number of responses from patients from different age groups, detailed in Table 2. 26.3% of the patients have a learning disability. Responses were gathered from across the UK, with the highest representation from Greater London (23.7%), followed by South West (18.4%), South East (13.2%) and North West (13.2%). 92.1% of the persons with epilepsy have not had any form of surgery for epilepsy and 86.8% have a VNS device. The complete demographic characteristics of the survey respondents are detailed in Table 2 (see Supplementary material).

Figure 3. Patients’ (n=38) consideration of VNS or DBS as treatment options. A, Likert plot illustrates the likelihood of patients to consider VNS or DBS as a treatment option and indicates a higher likelihood of patients considering VNS compared to DBS. B, bar chart presents factors that deter patients from considering neuromodulation as a treatment option and highlights the prevalence of each factor affecting patient decision-making.

Section 3-4:

The proportion of respondents likely to consider VNS stands at 31.6%, and 34.2% showing a likelihood to consider DBS (Figure 3A).

The key factors that dissuade persons with epilepsy from considering these as a treatment option are the thought of the procedure, the associated side effects, and the requirement for battery change. Some other factors under the graphed category ‘Other’ entered as comments by respondents were- ‘Epilepsy isn’t severe enough to undergo treatment,’ ‘Inability to come off some of current medication.’ (Figure 3B)

Patients identified several key treatment goals (Figure 4A), with the highest priority being improving quality of life (81.6%). Other highly rated goals included reducing the risk of sudden unexpected death (76.3%), achieving seizure freedom (76.3%), and reducing seizures (76.3%). Enhancing concentration and mood were also considered important, each receiving 68.4%, while improving sleep was valued at 65.8%.

The survey stated that risks of DBS and VNS are slightly different as one is an operation on the brain and the other is an operation in the neck. Figure 4B shows how important patients/carers would consider the risks. Patients/carers were informed in the survey that VNS requires battery changes every 2-4 years, which is usually performed as a day case operation under general anaesthesia. Some DBS systems offer the option of being able to wirelessly recharge the battery, which can last up to 30 years. The modal response was 5 (very important) on the Likert scale of 1 to 5, with 73.7% respondents considering this difference between the two treatments important.

Figure 4. Patient (n=38) views on potential randomised trial. A, Likert plot illustrates patient opinions on the importance of treatment goals and provides insight into which is considered most critical by patients. B, Likert plot displays patient views on the importance of various risks associated with the potential trial, each with a 1 in 100 chance of occurring; it illustrates how patients weigh the significance of these risks. C, bar chart illustrates concerns related to the potential trial and the frequency of the concerns reported by patients.

52.6% respondents said that they would enter the proposed DoVE trial if they, as a person with epilepsy, or their partner or family member with epilepsy, would be referred. Some of the reasons for interest in participation included wanting to try DBS/VNS before epilepsy surgery as it is a less invasive option, the potential to improve quality of life and improve understanding of epilepsy treatments, wanting to try a method besides medications (that have not led to seizure freedom), and the exhaustion of all other options. The main reasons why they would not want to participate in the trial were the thought of "being used as a guinea pig", fear of surgery, fear of side effects, and the discomfort of being randomly assigned into one of the treatments.

73.7% respondents agreed that if the person with epilepsy has a learning disability, it would be ethical to get permission to participate in the study from their carer or next-of-kin. These surveyors commented that the carer or next-of-kin making the decision would be safer. The respondents who thought this would be unethical said that both the person with epilepsy

with a learning disability and their carer or next-of-kin, should be involved in making this decision.

The most recurring response (76.3%) with regards to concerns over a trial were the risks of the treatments. 63.2% of patients/carers were concerned about not knowing which treatment is more effective and/or about missing the treatment option they wanted more (Figure 4C). 84.2% of respondents would prefer to be offered both treatments and choose which to proceed with.

Another concern in 15.8% of respondents was the additional assessments and appointments associated with the trial. It was stated in the survey that in trials like these the patient in the trial would be assessed at multiple time points to see how they are doing, which would come at a travel and convenience cost. 50% respondents thought that a visit every 3 months would be most convenient, while 26.3% thought a visit once a month would be appropriate.

Patients and their carers were asked about what factors would encourage them to participate in the trial if it were offered to them. 78.4% would take part to contribute towards better care of people with epilepsy. 70.3% said that the potential to receive new treatments would encourage them and 56.8% would take part to help find out which treatment is best. 48.6% would be encouraged by the closer care they would receive (Figure 5A). Among 'Other' factors were "Possibility of reducing number of medications taken," "Recognition by the team of the psychological impacts on individuals participating as well as the neurological effects," and "Potential to stop all seizures and end side effects from medication."

It was then important to learn what factors would encourage potential trial participants to stay in the trial. Patients and their carers picked close follow-up (83.8%), compensation for travel and visits (59.5%), and relaxed or infrequent follow-up (18.9%) as the top factors (Figure 5B). 2 respondents suggested that follow-up appointments be a hybrid of video calls and in-person visits.

Figure 5. Patient interest to participate in potential randomised trial. A, bar chart shows patient responses regarding factors that would encourage their participation in a trial and provides insights into incentives for patient enrolment. B, bar chart shows patient responses regarding factors that would encourage them to stay in a trial rather than withdraw and provides insights into aspects that influence patient retention.

Discussion:

The survey results offer a selective overview of both clinician and patient/carer perspectives on neuromodulation for DRE in the UK, making the case for further studies to compare and optimise these treatments.

Clinicians prioritized seizure reduction as the primary outcome but also emphasized seizure freedom and quality of life. While clinicians expressed willingness to participate in the proposed trial by referring patients, there appears to be a discord between clinicians' willingness to contribute to the trial and their views on the ethics of randomization, potentially highlighting complex challenges that could arise if the trial were to move forward. On the patient and carer side, VNS was more likely to be considered compared to DBS, but overall, about half expressed a willingness to participate in the trial. Key reasons for trial participation included the exhaustion of other treatment options, altruism, and the hope of achieving meaningful treatment goals (Figure 4A).

The disparity in the endorsement of VNS and DBS by clinicians likely reflects the established status of VNS, which was introduced in the UK in the early 2000s and gained wider adoption after the NICE issued guidance in 2012 recommending its use as an add-on therapy for DRE (16). By contrast, DBS is a more recent addition in the UK. NICE issued guidance in 2018, conditionally approving DBS as a treatment for DRE in adults, currently restricted to the ANT under strict governance (12).

VNS is a widely used treatment option in treating DRE in children and adults (17). While there are no randomised controlled trials that have investigated the efficacy of DBS in paediatric patients, its promising outcomes in adults, and growing evidence of safety and efficacy in children, make it a potential option for children (18). Our clinician survey reveals varying opinions on the minimum age to consider DBS, with a higher modal age and large interquartile range compared to VNS, which is often recommended for younger patients. This caution reflects uncertainty about DBS, stemming from limited evidence and potential risks, particularly in children. These gaps underscore the need for targeted randomised controlled trials, such as the proposed DoVE trial, to clarify DBS's role and optimize outcomes for this demographic (19).

Our findings of clinician views on primary outcomes relates to the metrics seen in neuromodulation trials (20–23) and aligns with expert opinions highlighted in Kaufmann et al. that outcome evaluation should extend beyond seizure metrics to include neurocognitive function, mood, and quality of life (24). Kaufmann et. al noted that ‘optimal outcome is only achieved if patient expectations are met besides significant improvement in clinical parameters’ (24). This suggests that any future trials, must account for a range of clinical and patient-centred outcomes to comprehensively evaluate treatment efficacy.

Patient/carer-reported key treatment goals that closely align with the literature. There are at least seven distinct goals of epilepsy treatment: to reduce seizure frequency and severity, to improve function, to enhance quality of life, to promote coping, to improve external circumstances, to prevent premature death, and (in children) to promote growth and development (25). Achieving seizure freedom is particularly significant considering the International League Against Epilepsy task force’s definition of drug-resistant epilepsy as the “failure of adequate trials of two tolerated, appropriately chosen and used ASM schedules (monotherapy or in combination) to achieve sustained seizure freedom” (26).

Notably, the efficacy of VNS and DBS in achieving seizure freedom plays a role in patient decision-making. Seizure-free intervals of at least 6 months were observed in 18% of DBS-

ANT patients, and VNS has a variable seizure-free rate ranging from 7-20% (27). Furthermore, the lower rate of SUDEP in patients treated with neurostimulation is an important consideration. SUDEP rates were found to be significantly lower in both DBS-ANT (2.0 per 1000 patient years) and VNS (2.3 per 1000 patient years) compared to those seen in typical DRE patients (27), but these figures are still quite low overall and may not substantially influence treatment decisions.

Balzekas et al. (28) provide insights into patient and carer priorities, highlighting that neuromodulation therapies such as VNS and DBS are often viewed as a “last remaining option” after failure of ASMs. Patients/carers prioritize improving quality of life, reducing seizures, and regaining independence, even without guaranteed seizure freedom. However, the study also reveals notable concerns about the risks and invasiveness of DBS, including potential complications such as stroke and infection, which temper patient enthusiasm (28). Despite these apprehensions, potential improvements drive willingness, underscoring the need to manage expectations and address safety concerns.

Our study also reveals significant concerns that could affect trial participation, including the perceived risks associated with surgery and uncertainty about which treatment option would be more effective. DBS involves higher perioperative risks compared to VNS, with complications such as intracranial haemorrhage (4.5% of implants), infections (12.7% at 10 years), and lead misplacement (8.2%) (27). Serious complications, such as tract haemorrhage, occur in less than 5% of cases, and mortality is very rare. DBS may also have preliminary associations with mood and memory effects, although most adverse effects are transient and related to stimulation parameters (1). In contrast, VNS has a lower risk profile, with complications typically like superficial infections (3–6%) and sometimes infections requiring device removal, vocal cord paralysis, and bradycardia/asystole (20,21,27,29). Unique risks include hoarseness and cough from recurrent laryngeal nerve involvement and potential effects on sleep apnoea, though permanent risks are less than 3% (1,20,21,23,29). While neuromodulation devices are generally safe, issues like lead breakage and other device-related issues remain concerns (1,29). A significant concern with ANT DBS reported in Salanova et.al was a gradual worsening in neuropsychological composite scores over time, with increased depression ($p=0.039$), anxiety ($p=0.027$), and total mood disturbance ($p=0.0016$) (29,30). Despite these issues, improvements were observed in attention, executive function, and subjective cognitive function (all $p<0.001$), suggesting some cognitive benefits alongside the adverse outcomes (29,30). These differences in surgical risks and potential complications between DBS and VNS may influence patient decisions and their willingness to participate in trials.

Patients and carers expressed a strong preference for choosing between VNS and DBS rather than being randomly assigned, reflecting a shared concern with Balzekas et al.'s findings about maintaining autonomy in treatment decisions. Addressing these concerns will be critical to ensuring the success of potential comparative studies. Providing detailed information, managing patient expectations, and offering thorough counselling can help overcome these barriers. Reflecting to the clinicians' view on treatment randomization, transparency and thorough counselling will be essential to build confidence and encourage participation from both clinicians and patients. These findings suggest that beyond the scientific and medical value of the trial, its design must address logistical and practical aspects that affect patient convenience and perceived benefit.

A key finding from this study is that patients value the battery differences between VNS and DBS. Current VNS systems do not have rechargeable options, necessitating more frequent revisions (27). Furthermore, rechargeable devices depend on patient compliance for optimal

performance, as missed recharges can reduce efficacy. Thus, patient preference for DBS may stem from its longer-lasting rechargeable batteries and lower long-term maintenance (27).

Retention rates can be defined as the percentage of patients who maintain the neuromodulation device at established time points (31). It provides an essential perspective on the long-term utility and patient satisfaction with neurostimulation therapies for epilepsy. VNS studies show varying retention rates, ranging from 35% to 94% in the literature (20,22,31). The reasons for device explanation included non-efficacy or worsening seizures, MRI requirements for other medical needs, infection, ASM success, and vocal cord paralysis (29). In an ANT-DBS study, the 5-year retention rate was 68.2%. The reasons included implant site infection, non-efficacy, anxiety, amongst others (29,30). These findings highlight the importance of individual tolerance and efficacy in determining long-term retention and underscore the need for strategies to minimize complications and improve patient satisfaction in both treatments. Modern DBS and VNS systems are MRI conditional, and patients can safely be imaged if required, although VNS has an exclusion zone incorporating the thoracic and upper lumbar spine.

Limitations

Given the unknown size of the distribution lists for both surveys, calculating an exact response rate was not possible. However, it is likely that the response rate for both surveys was very low. This limitation raises important concerns about the external validity of the responses. As the surveys were distributed exclusively to individuals affiliated with specific epilepsy charities and societies, the sample may not reflect the broader epilepsy population. Moreover, the survey data is only UK-based and may not capture the global variations in attitudes towards the treatments, concerns regarding them, and the readiness of the medical community to accept such treatments in their regime.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study highlights the current clinician and patient perspectives on VNS and DBS, providing a strong rationale for a well-designed randomised controlled trial. The DoVE trial, incorporating patient-centred outcomes and addressing the concerns raised in these surveys, has the potential to contribute significantly to the treatment landscape for drug-resistant epilepsy. By including both efficacy and quality of life as primary outcomes, the trial will align with the needs and preferences of both clinicians and patients and their carers, offering a comprehensive evaluation of these neuromodulation techniques.

Supplementary Material:

Link to video embedded in patients survey: <http://youtube.com/watch?v=jVzndd1KJg8>

Demographic variable	Response	N (%)
Speciality	Neurosurgery	13 (40.6%)
	Neurology	13 (40.6%)
	Neurophysiology	6 (18.8%)
Number of years as a consultant	<10 years	12 (37.5%)
	10-20 years	14 (43.8%)
	>20 years	6 (18.8%)
Region of the UK working in	Greater London	8 (25%)
	South East	7 (21.9%)
	Yorkshire and the Humber	4 (12.5%)
	East of England	3 (9.4%)
	Scotland	3 (9.4%)
	South West	3 (9.4%)
	North West	2 (6.3%)
	West Midlands	1 (3.1%)
	Wales	1 (3.1%)
	Northern Ireland	0
	East Midlands	0
	North East	0

Table 1. Demographics of Clinicians, N=32

Demographic variable	Response	N (%)
Age group	0-19	10 (26.3%)
	20-39	10 (26.3%)
	40-59	10 (26.3%)
	60+	8 (21.2%)
Region of the UK working in	Greater London	9 (23.7%)
	South West	7 (18.4%)
	Soth East	5 (13.2%)
	North West	5 (13.2%)
	Wales	3 (7.9%)
	East Midlands	3 (7.9%)
	North East	2 (5.3%)
	Yorkshire and the Humber	2 (5.3%)
	West Midlands	1 (2.6%)
	Scotland	1 (2.6%)
	East of England	0
	Northern Ireland	0

Table 2. Demographics of Patients/Carers, N=38

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